

Physico-Chemical Studies on Some Alkylmercapto- and Alkylsulphonyl Phenols

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Electric dipole moments, dissociation constants and uv absorption spectra have been determined for two alkylmercapto phenols and two alkylsulphonyl phenols. The results are examined with a view to ascertaining whether or not the 3d orbitals of the sulphur atom participate in resonance.

DESPITE extensive physicochemical investigations on a variety of organic sulphur compounds, no unequivocal conclusion has been reached regarding the participation of the 3d orbitals of the sulphur atom in resonance interaction¹. In the case of compounds containing the bivalent sulphur atom, it has been generally observed that significant (d-p) π type of resonance interaction involving the participation of the 3d orbitals of the sulphur atom takes place in the ground state as well as in the excited state in alkyl aryl sulphides, provided a sufficiently strong electron releasing group is present *para* to the alkylmercapto group². A similar conclusion has also been reached for alkyl aryl sulphones from a study of dipole moments³, dissociation constants⁴ and uv absorption spectra⁵ of a number of alkyl aryl sulphones. As part of our investigation of a large number of 4-alkylthioanilines and 4-alkylsulphonylanilines, we have found from a study of dipole moments, dissociation constants and uv absorption spectra that significant (d-p) π conjugation does take place in these types of molecules^{4,6,7}. In view of the fact that the chemical reactivity of anilines and phenols are comparable, we have initiated a parallel study on 4-alkylmercapto- and 4-alkylsulphonylphenols with a view to finding out whether or not the hydroxyl group can enter into significant (d-p) π conjugation with the alkylmercapto and alkylsulphonyl groups. With this object in view, we have prepared two 4-alkylmercapto phenols and two 4-alkylsulphonylphenols and determined their electric dipole moments, dissociation constants and uv absorption spectra.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Preparation of compounds: 4-Methylmercapto-phenol (1) was prepared by diazotising 4-methylthioaniline with sodium nitrite and sulphuric acid, crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 84-85°

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(lit m.p. 84-85°), yield 50%. 3-Methyl-4-methylmercapto-phenol (2) was prepared in a similar manner by diazotising 3-methyl-4-methylthioaniline, crystallised from petroleum ether. m.p. 55° (lit m.p. 55-56°), yield 47%. 4-Methylsulphonylphenol (3) was prepared by oxidising 1 with 30% (by volume) hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid, crystallised from benzene, m.p. 91° (lit m.p. 91°), yield 90%. 3-Methyl-4-methylsulphonylphenol (4) was prepared in a similar manner by oxidising 2, crystallised from benzene, m.p. 103°, yield 85%. Found: C, 51.90; H, 5.50; S, 17.15%. Calcd. for C₈H₁₀O₂S; C, 51.61; H, 5.38; S 17.20%.

Dipole moment measurements: The dipole moments of the mercapto-phenols and sulphonylphenols were determined in benzene and dioxane respectively, at 40°. The method and equipment used were the same as that reported earlier^{6,7}.

Dissociation constant determinations: The dissociation constants of the alkylmercapto-phenols and alkylsulphonylphenols were determined by the spectrophotometric method of Robinson and Biggs^{8,9}. Borax buffers were used in the case of alkylmercapto-phenols and phosphate buffers were used in the case of alkylsulphonylphenols. The pK_a values obtained correspond to thermodynamic dissociation constants since the corrections for the activity coefficients of the ions have been made. The temperature of measurement was 25°.

Results and Discussion

Electric dipole moments: The electric dipole moments of the two 4-methylmercapto-phenols and the two 4-methylsulphonylphenols are presented in Table 1. The dipole moments of these compounds calculated by the vector addition method are also presented in Table 1 for comparison. For the purpose of the vector addition method, the following group moments (μ_i) and group angles (θ_i) have been used: -OH, $\mu=1.55$ D, $\theta=90^\circ$; -SCH₃, $\mu=1.34$ D, $\theta=77.5^\circ$; -SO₂CH₃, $\mu=4.73$ D, $\theta=117^\circ$ and -CH₃, $\mu=0.37$ D, $\theta=0.11^\circ$.

TABLE 1—ELECTRIC DIPOLE MOMENTS OF 4-METHYLMERCAPTO- AND 4-METHYLSULPHONYLPHENOLS

Phenol	$\mu_{\text{Obsd.}}/D$	$\mu_{\text{Calcd.}}/D$	$\mu_{\text{Obsd.}}/D - \mu_{\text{Calcd.}}/D$
4-Methylmercapto-3-Methyl-4-methylmercapto-	2.10	2.05	0.05
4-Methylsulphonyl-3-Methyl-4-methylsulphonyl-	5.70	4.97	0.73
4-methylsulphonyl-	5.80	4.91	0.89

The difference between $\mu_{\text{Obsd.}}$ and $\mu_{\text{Calcd.}}$ is taken to be a measure of mesomeric interaction of the -OH group with -SCH₃ or -SO₂CH₃ group, as the case may be. From the table, it is obvious that in the case of the methyl mercaptophenols the difference is negligible and hence significant (d-p) π conjugation is ruled out. On the other hand, the difference is quite considerable in the case of the methylsulphonylphenols indicating significant (d-p) π conjugation involving structure A (Fig. 1) in the ground state.

Fig. 1. (d-p) π Interaction in 4-methylsulphonylphenol.

Structure A involves the participation of the vacant 3d orbitals of the sulphur atom. This observation is in line with the views of Price according to whom the electron accepting properties of the sulphur atom will be prominent when the sulphur atom bears a partial positive character^{1,2}.

Dissociation constants: Dissociation constants of the two 4-methylmercaptophenols and the two 4-methylsulphonylphenols at 25° are presented in Table 2. The pK_a values for 4-methylmercaptophenol and 4-methylsulphonylphenol agree well with the values reported (9.53 and 7.89, respectively) by Bordwell and Cooper^{1,3}. As expected, the introduction of a methyl group into the phenyl ring does not cause any significant change in the pK_a of the parent compound. Inspection of the results of Table 2 reveals the interesting fact that the acid strengthening effect of the methylsulphonyl

TABLE 2—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF 4-METHYLMERCAPTO- AND 4-METHYLSULPHONYLPHENOLS AT 25°

Phenol	pK_a
4-Methylmercapto-	9.61
3-Methyl-4-methylmercapto-	9.71
4-Methylsulphonyl-	7.89
3-Methyl-4-methylsulphonyl-	7.92

group on the parent phenol is much greater than that of methylmercapto group (pK_a of phenol = 9.98, pK_a of *m*-cresol = 10.1 at 25°). This is again in consonance with the conclusions arrived at from dipole moment studies because resonance structures

such as A will tend to increase the acidity of the phenol. Thus, the dissociation constants data also point to significant (d-p) π conjugation in the case of 4-alkylsulphonylphenols but not in the case of 4-alkylmercaptophenols.

UV spectral data: UV absorption spectral data in 96 per cent ethanol for the four compounds studied are presented in Table 3. For two of these

TABLE 3—UV SPECTRAL DATA FOR 4-METHYLMERCAPTO- AND 4-METHYLSULPHONYLPHENOLS

Phenol	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}
4-Methylmercapto-	280	6920
	255	7080
	285	1070
3-Methyl-4-methylmercapto-	285	9100
	255	7580
	287	1660
4-Methylsulphonyl-	240	15850
	268	1580
3-Methyl-4-methylsulphonyl-	242	18500
	270	2000

compounds, viz., 4-methylmercaptophenol and 4-methylsulphonylphenol, uv data have been already reported by Fehnel and Carmack^{1,4} and our values agree well with the reported values. Further, the spectral behaviour 3-methyl-substituted phenols is virtually the same as the corresponding parent methylmercapto- and methylsulphonylphenols. In the case of the methylmercaptophenols, the uv data indicate no significant mesomeric interaction since the spectra of these compounds are not very different from those of the corresponding methylmercaptobenzenes. For methyl phenyl sulphide, for example, there are two bands—one at 254 nm ($\epsilon = 9550$) and the other at 275 nm ($\epsilon = 1410$). This implies that there is no significant (d-p) π conjugation in the excited state in these two compounds. On the other hand, the methylsulphonylphenols exhibit significant bathochromic shifts with reference to the corresponding methylsulphonylbenzenes. For methyl phenyl sulphone for example there are two bands—one at 217 nm ($\epsilon = 6760$) and the other at 275 nm ($\epsilon = 1410$). The band at 217 nm is bathochromically shifted by 23 nm and the intensity of the band increases by more than 20 times. This is indicative of (d-p) π interaction in the methylsulphonylanilines in the excited state leading to structures such as A (Fig. 1).

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